

Two modified CPV models along with their comparison

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Abstract—Concentrated photovoltaic system is a technique that uses the sunlight effectively especially those CPV systems have better performance which uses multi junction solar cells. This paper presents two modified CPV designs of a simple PV model. The first model is a 5 stage CPV system that includes greater number of reflectors while the second model is a 4 stage CPV system that distributes the collimated rays uniformly on the solar cell. The sunlight rays first strike at the primary reflector which is taken as parabolic trough in both the models. These rays then reflect through some secondary reflectors and pass through the Fresnel lens that focus the light into a Plano-concave lens and then this concentrated sunlight is distributed uniformly on the surface of the Multi junction solar cell. Our model also includes extra solar cell placed around the Multi Junction solar cell comparably less cost which is used to detect the diffused light. CPV systems using multijunction solar cells provides more power at the output. The efficiency and uniformity of the irradiance of both the models were analyzed as compared to simple PV model with single junction solar cell and conclusion is concluded.

Index Terms— CPV systems, multi junction solar cells, irradiation, Parabolic trough, Fresnel lens, Plano-concave lens.

I. INTRODUCTION

CPV systems are Concentrated Photovoltaic Systems. It is used to convert the sunlight into electricity by focusing the sunlight into various reflectors and finally entering the Multijunction Solar cells. It has greater efficiency as compared to simple PV system [1]. CPV system includes lens that is used to focus light, a tracker that keeps on tracking the sunlight and a receiver at the end where all the rays are fallen [2]. There are two main factors that affect the performance of a CPV system. The first factor is the efficiency of the reflectors (primary and secondary) and the second factor depends upon the uniform irradiance, to overcome this factor Multijunction solar cells are used [14]. Uniform irradiance means that the distribution of the concentrated sunlight on the junction is consistent [3]. Third factor is the acceptance angle of the lens. A perfect, absolute and supreme CPV system is one which transfers the total sunlight entering the primary reflectors to the Multijunction solar cell.

There are mainly two great issues in Photovoltaic systems. The first issue is the Non consistent illumination which has further two types. The first type occurs when the highly concentrated sunlight falls on a point rather than whole cell causing unnecessarily and absurdly lighting at that point, as a result huge current is produced, and the voltage drops [11]. The

second type occurs because there is some area on the cell where either very few rays or no rays are fallen, as a result the output of the solar cell is reduced [4]. This problem leads to second issue, when this sunlight is not uniformly distributed over the cell some part of the cell gets heated which reduces the life of cell. So, some particular and unusual arrangement is done for the cooling of the cell. Some cooling system uses air, water etc. PCM technique known as Phase Change Materials is very efficiently used now a days for cooling [5]. It has high cost but due to the advantage that it can absorb and supply heat energy and can make use of the misused heat, the cell's temperature is reduced and as a result the efficiency of the system is increased. Heat sinks are also used to reduce the cell's temperature by dividing the temperature equally and steadily over the cell. Many solutions were presented to handle this non consistent illumination issue in CPV systems. One technique is to improve the design of the lens to achieve a consistent distribution of the flux of the collimated sunlight and get maximum power to enhance the efficiency. The second technique is by using SOE (Secondary Optical Element) [6]. In this method various reflectors are used to focus the sunlight uniformly over the multijunction solar cell. It may have number of reflectors and respectively be a 2-stage, 3-stage, 4-stage or higher CPV systems. The third issue of a CPV systems is that the lens has small acceptance angle due to which the CPV systems are failed to absorb the diffused rays. The solution is provided in this paper. Another issue occurs when some parts of the cell are shaded. In that case the energy that is produced by the unshaded cell is dissipated into the shaded cell due to the series connection and as a result the total system energy output is reduced and hence the efficiency is reduced [7].

Single-junction solar cells can only utilize a fraction of the energy of incident light. Spectral utilization of the Air Mass ratio 1.5 of a single-junction Crystalline-Si solar cell shows us that it has a bandgap energy of 1.12 electron volts and a wavelength of 1.1 micrometers. Photons that has wavelength lesser than 1.1 μ m losses all its energy above 1.12eV due to extra energy, whereas those photons that have greater wavelength greater than 1.1 μ m loses its energy due to insufficient energy to excite and electron. Hence a lot of photon energy is lost through this thermalization process. The efficiency of single junction is around 25%. Values of bandgap energy and wavelengths of some elements are shown in Table 1. [8]

Table I
BANDGAP ENERGIES FOR SINGLE JUNCTION

Quantity	Bandgap (eV)	Wavelength (um)
Si	1.12	1.11
GaAs	1.14	0.87
CdTe	1.5	0.83
InP	1.35	0.92

Multijunction Solar cells allows us to get better efficiency. It decreases the transmission as well as the thermalization losses, but its disadvantage is that it has very high cost. Multijunction cells are not found as flat solar panels as compared to the 1 junction solar cell, instead the concentrated sunlight is made focus on some reflectors and then injected into the solar cell that has very small area. As the Multijunction solar cell can absorb very high concentrated rays hence this gives us advantage to decrease the solar cell body by hundreds to thousand times.

Research shows that the (III-V) multijunction solar cells has high efficiency achieved in converting the sun rays into electricity is achieved by using as compared to the conventional solar cell which has only one layer of semiconductor stuff [9]. Study shows that the cell placed at the bottom consisting of Ge as base has a bandgap of 0.67eV. The cell placed in the middle having substrate Ga_{0.99}In_{0.01}As as base has a bandgap of 1.35eV and the cell placed on the top having substrate Ga_{0.5}In_{0.5}P as base has a bandgap of 1.86eV. These cells are separated by tunnel junction. Spectral utilization of a triple junction solar cell shows us that the top cell is high bandgap absorber, the middle cell absorbs bandgap having normal values and bottom cell absorbs low bandgap energies. Incident light first passes through the high bandgap absorber material. High energy photons are absorbed by the top cell. The normal energy photons are absorbed by the second absorber layer with corresponding low bandgap and the least energy photons are absorbed by the third absorber layer with the least bandgap. By connecting three solar cells with absorber layers of different bandgap, we reduce the non-absorption and the excess energy lost through thermalization [10]. The resulting open circuit is the sum of open-circuit voltages of individual cells while the short circuit current density is limited by the lowest current density delivered by the top cell. However, adding more and more junctions adds the complexity to the cell and to the fabrication process. This will increase cost to the production.

A Fresnel lens used in the models gives us advantage to use less material as compared to other traditional lens, so it has less area. There are two basic types of Fresnel lens. The first type is Non imaging and second is imaging. In both the models we will be using spherical imaging Fresnel lens whose function is to pivot all the rays into a single point and hence providing a clear and keen image [11]. The second type is non imaging lens which don't create clear images. Parabolic trough, as the name suggests has a shape like parabola. It is a reflector in which if the rays are fallen in the direction of the plane of symmetry (the axis around which if the parabola is rotated, it remains the same) these rays are focused at a single point. Inclined flat mirrors are used to concentrate the collimated rays and sends

them towards the convex reflector for further reflection in Model 1. The rays after getting reflected from this convex reflector move towards the concave reflector. Concave reflector is used in both the models for the purpose to make the rays parallel and sends the concentrated rays towards the Fresnel lens [12]. This Fresnel lens further sends the rays towards the Plano-concave lens in model. A Plano-concave lens as shown in the model 2 has one flat surface at the top and a curve surface at the bottom. The rays after getting entered into this lens are uniformly distributed towards the multijunction solar cell (III-V) to get better irradiance consistency [12].

Our proposed model not only just gives us better consistent uniformity, but it also gives us one more advantage by collecting the diffused solar rays. The model 2 has some CPV components along with some solar cell of low cost. Every single CPV component has a POE known as Primary Optical Element which is taken as Fresnel lens, SOE known as Secondary Optical Element is taken as Plano-concave lens and multijunction solar cell in both the models. The SOE allows us to get better irradiance uniformity in a particular CPV component whereas as the diffused sun rays are absorbed by the extra solar cell as discussed above [13]. Hence in such a way our model gives us better consistent irradiation along with greater system efficiency.

II. DESIGN

A general traditional junction (3 stage) CPV system is shown in figure 1. Our both models are a modified version of this simple CPV system. The basic motive is to somehow increase the efficiency and the output power [20]. The first model uses greater number of reflectors that convert the rays from a large area to a small 3 junction solar cell whereas in the second method a Plano-concave lens is used as SOE, that distributes the rays uniformly on the multijunction solar cell. The first modified model includes the inclined flat mirror while the other don't. The incoming sunlight gets reflected by the parabolic trough and is spread to various secondary reflectors.

Fig. 1 Simple Photo-Voltaic system with single junction solar cell

These rays then get concentrated by the Fresnel lens and then it is diffused uniquely on the multijunction solar cells by the Plano-concave lens. The extra Si solar cell placed around the Plano concave lens are used to absorb the diffused rays. Moreover, these cheap cells also help us in achieving those rays which were unable to strike at the Fresnel lens.[13]

Fig. 2 (MODEL 1) Five stages CPV model with three junction solar cell

Half of the convex reflector is used according to the assumptions, the other half unused may be used to capture the diffused rays, however the rays are concentrated heavily each time the rays get reflected by the lens. The convex reflector uses its inner surface and concave reflector uses its outer surface for reflection. The rays after getting reflected by the convex reflector in model 1 or parabolic trough in model 2 moves towards its focal point but as the concave reflector is placed in between, the rays strike at the outer region of this reflector and then the rays are dispersed in parallel towards the Fresnel lens.

Fig. 3 (MODEL 2) Four stages CPV model with three junction solar cell

III. METHOD

In first modified model, fig 2. There are four incoming rays named as (r1, r2, r3 and r4) that gets reflected at the parabolic trough placed at the left at corner points (S1, S2, S3 and S4) and move towards the inclined flat mirror named as secondary reflector(K2,K3,K1,K4). Similarly, four incoming rays named as (r5, r6, r7, and r8) gets reflected at the parabolic trough placed at the right side at points (S5, S6, S7 and S8) and move towards the inclined flat mirror named as secondary reflector(K6, K7, K5 and K8). The rays getting reflected from (K2 and K4) from the inclined flat mirror gets reflected from the convex reflector placed at down left at points (L2 and L4) and move towards the concave reflector at points (M2 and M4). Similarly, the rays getting reflected from the points (K6 and K8) from the second inclined mirror gets reflected from the convex reflector placed at downright at corner points (L6 and L8) and move towards the same unique concave reflector used in the model at points (M6 and M8). Point to be noted is that the length of the inclined flat mirror is greater than the length of the convex reflector. The basic purpose is to concentrate the light by reducing the area of the next reflector where the concentrated rays are made to be fallen [14]. This is the reason that the intensity of the rays are very high when they reach to the multijunction solar cell and hence gives us more output power. Now we will only be using the corner points for the sake of complexity. The rays getting reflected from (M4 and M8) from the concave reflector moves in parallel and enter the Fresnel lens at points (N4 and N8) which focus these concentrated rays uniformly at the multijunction solar cells [19]

Fig. 4 Block Diagram of model 2

Fig. 5 (MODEL 2) 3D image for Four stages CPV model with three junction solar cell

In the second modified model, fig 2. Same technique is used, the only difference is that no inclined flat mirror is used instead a Plano-concave lens is used to distribute the collimated rays uniquely with equal spacing on the multi junction solar cell, the rays (r_2 and r_4) and (r_6 and r_8) after getting reflected from the parabolic trough same as stated in model 1 at points (S2 and S4) and (S6 and S8) move directly towards the concave reflector at points (M2, M4, M8 and M6) and then move in parallel towards the Fresnel lens which then sends the rays towards the SOE (Plano concave lens) and finally the rays are injected into the multijunction solar cell uniformly. The block diagram of model 2 is shown in figure 4 where the arrows indicate the direction of the sunlight from primary reflector to receiver. The 3D model of this designed novel diagram is shown in fig.5. A few rays are only drawn in the model and secondly the lenses used are shown big in size just to show the direction of the sunlight clearly how they get reflected and strike at the 3 junction solar cell but practically they are very small in size and these rays are uniformly distributed at the receiver.

IV. RESULTS

The percentage of loss is increased to around 5% if secondary optical element is used in the system [17]. However, this loss is reimbursed as the extra Silicon solar cell is used of low cost to capture the diffused rays. Moreover, as the SOE is used in our second model, the lifetime of the multijunction solar cell is increased as compared to first designed CPV model without SOE, because it distributes the rays uniquely and steadily avoiding any hot sharp points over the cell.

Optical Power Ratio is the ratio of the of the concentrated rays that is sustained by the multijunction solar cell to the rays that were entered the POE (Fresnel lens). Results showed that the Optical Power Ratio of our second planned model i.e., using

the CPV system along with extra silicon solar cell having low cost and SOE (Plano concave lens) is higher as compared to the traditional CPV systems which has either only SOE or do not have both, SOE and extra silicon solar cell[13]

Conversion efficiency, which is basically the ratio of the power coming out from the CPV system to the power input from the sun rays. The percentage efficiency of the whole system depends upon the Conversion efficiency of the multijunction solar cell and strength of the incoming rays. As our second designed model can achieve both the direct concentrated rays as well as the diffused rays so in this case the conversion efficiency is higher as it depends on both the rays and this increase in system efficiency was achieved by some advanced factor of this designed CPV system i.e., using Silicon solar cell of low cost when compared to the first model that don't include the extra solar cell. [15]

System cost is another main factor that tells us whether the system is reliable and practical or not. Our first model is a 5 stage CPV system which includes more number of reflectors as compared to model 2, hence it is not cost effective, whereas on the other hand as our second proposed CPV model which is a four stage CPV system, includes the extra Silicon solar cell, the cost of the system no doubt, increases as compared to the traditional CPV system as shown in figure 1, but this effect is compensated because in this designed CPV model we achieve more power at the Output because these extra silicon solar cells captures the diffused rays which are not absorbed in simple CPV system i.e., without extra solar cells.

In single junction solar cell, some of the energy around 20.2% is lost because the photons have less energy to excite and electron and around 30.2% of energy is lost by those photons which have extra energy more than required to excite an electron. So, the theoretical efficiency equals 49.6% [18]. However, there are some other losses that reduces this factor and gives an efficiency of around 22%. Some electrons get recombine with the holes before they put up for the flow of current, cell's internal resistance denoted as R_i , photons that are reflected back after striking the cell or because they pass across the cell or because they are choked by the metal components placed over the cell. Our general single junction CPV (3 stage) system as shown in figure 1 has an efficiency around 26%.

By increasing the number of junctions increases the efficiency of the system. The efficiency of a 3-junction solar cell is found to be around 42%. It was found that the efficiency of the system is increased by a factor of 5% if we use 4 junctions instead of 3 junction solar cell and a further of 3% efficiency is increased if we use 5 junctions instead of 4 [16]. But since the cost of the Multijunction solar cells increases drastically as the number of junctions increases and looking into the economical reliability, we have used 3 junction solar cell in our designed model along with extra solar cells to absorb the diffused rays.

There are plenty of losses stages in both the designed models. The first loss is in the Primary reflection, secondly loss is in the secondary reflection, then there are many losses in the number of reflectors placed in both the models and then in the end there are some losses in the PV Cell itself. So our first model has an overall efficiency of around 32% due to the losses

occurred in the number of reflectors and the second modified model has an efficiency of 40% because it has less number of reflectors moreover it has the ability to capture the concentrated rays as well as the diffused rays which increases its efficiency, the 3 junction solar cell also plays a vital role in the enhancement of the system efficiency and the generated output energy [16].

V. CONCLUSION

We proposed two novel CPV models in this paper. Both of our designed model has high optical power ratio, high conversion efficiency, produce more energy at the output. Model 2 specifically distributes the collimated rays uniformly over the 3 junction solar cells with the help of SOE along with extra Silicon solar cell, used to absorb the diffused rays. **We have used a parabolic trough as a primary reflector, it has its own loss.** 100% of the light is not reflected in the secondary reflector, some is absorbed by the mirror, some light is not reflected to the secondary mirror, so these rays are lost as it reflects out. The thickness of the mirror is kept very small for keeping the least amount of metal connected to the dish in order to least the amount of hotness. Greater the temperature, greater will be the losses. Concentrated light is injected into the secondary reflector which gets hot because it is focused and concentrated. Then this concentrated light is injected further to a series of reflectors which gets hotter further due to high density of energy of the rays. In the end this concentrated light is injected into the 3-junction solar cell. CPV has higher efficiency as compared to simple PV cell because bigger area of light is focused on smaller area of light which ultimately gives us energy. Comparing the efficiency of both the designed models we found that Model 1 has a greater number of reflectors as compared to model 2 although it provides more concentrated rays. Model 2 includes SOE, that distributes these collimated rays uniformly over the multijunction solar cell and knowing the fact that each reflector has its own losses and the cost of model 1 is higher than model 2 due to more number of reflectors so, economically model 2 (4-Stages CPV system) is more preferred over model 1.

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